

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essentials of a Good Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-6)
4. The Place of Latin Expressions and Abbreviations in Everyday Use (EUCLID 2021, 56-61)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
6. Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-48)

SHARPEN THE TOOLS FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As a first study period for the ACA-401D, the course pack addresses some fundamentals in good academic writing. Haven worked professionally for several years in the field of public health, I was quite excited to commence this course and improve my academic writing skills to align with the high-quality international standards expected at the level of writing academic papers at a doctoral level. Importantly the study period served to broaden my appetite to discover more intricate details on good academic writing which I also hope to deploy in my professional setting as an international public health professional. The overviews provided while also being concise enough deserve constant application to improve my academic writing skills. I hope to acquire more on the specifics as I progress in the ACA-401D.

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2) ESSENTIALS OF A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

As an essential part of an academic course or program, writing a good essay takes on some level of importance. Academic writing purposes to persuade the reader of the validity of an idea while providing evidence to bolster the idea's credibility (EUCLID 2021, 1). The course pack further goes on to show how to structure and present a good essay with the aim of achieving objectives such as ensuring the essay answers a question and presents an argument, while discussing a thesis by way of providing evidence and sound reasoning. I can relate to the importance of having a good understanding of how to structure an academic essay as shown in the [ACA-401D](#) course pack. The material indicates that though the process of writing an essay could include drafting, organizing the materials, researching the topic, writing the essay, and editing the essay; however, these do not have to follow a particular order credibility (EUCLID 2021, 2-4). However, the material highlighted the need to ensure the essay is edited and appropriately structured in presenting the ideas to the reader as these will guarantee proper communication (EUCLID 2021, 4).

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In my professional practice as a public health supply chain expert, I have had numerous occasions to develop reports, abstracts, and other forms of communication to varied audiences. I can clearly relate to the need to be unambiguous in writing an essay and ensuring that there is clarity and coherence in my presentation, providing adequate depth and context to show a good grasp and knowledge of the subject matter while taking care to avoid grammatical errors, punctuation errors and presenting the communication in proper language that flows and is not complex to the reader. These align with the tips on writing a good academic essay by www.ultimateproofreader.co.uk.

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The tip in the course pack on writing good essays "Write the introduction and conclusion after the body" (EUCLID 2021, 1) agrees with Shona McCombes' advice stating "As you research and write, your argument might change focus or direction as you learn more. For this reason, it's often a good idea to wait until later in the writing process before you write the introduction paragraph—it can even be the very last thing you write" ([McCombes 2021](#)). I have found this practice very helpful as it gives you the freedom to develop your ideas without restriction and hence could improve the quality of your essay in terms of providing adequate context. In ensuring that the quality of your arguments and presentation are improved I found the following tip given in the course pack particularly interesting: "Most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing. If possible, put your essay aside for a few days before you begin to edit. This gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your work with a fresh perspective" (EUCLID 2021, 4). I have found that constructive arguments, debates and being open to different perspectives serve to enrich the knowledge base and approaches to issues and in academic context this plays a very important role in improving the body of knowledge on a subject matter or a thematic area, hence the advice in the EUCLID course pack to ask questions like "Have I answered the question as directly and comprehensively as possible? Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched? Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument?" (EUCLID 2021, 4). Answers to these questions form

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part of the overall revision and reflection that make up part of the editing phase of writing a good academic essay.

From the overall presentation of this topic, I was quite pleased with being able to relate with some previous experiences in academic writing while also happy to note certain pointers that will improve the writing and presenting experience for me in developing academic essays particularly. In the public health field where I practice, decisions are taken based on available data which are presented as evidence. As such it is important to ensure that communications, arguments, and academic writing are presented in a structured manner, with clarity and adequate context.

3) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

The historic rise of American English is mostly attributed to the growth of its economic power, wealth, education in addition to its increasing dominance of international politics, culture, and mass media with its attendant technology (EUCLID 2021, 7). Nigeria is a country colonized by the British while haven over the years absorbed a lot of American influence; these influences are reflected in the spoken and written English utilized by Nigerians with a mixture of types except where formal training has been conducted to ensuring adoption of one of the types. As such it was quite refreshing for me to see the distinctions in American and British English as presented in chapter six of the course pack.

As a Nigerian, though I have been previously aware of some differences in both types of English however I have not previously applied this distinction in writing to ensure an adherence to any of the types of English. Thus, it was quite educative to note the differences as highlighted by categories with samples in the course pack. For instance, for words with different spellings but the same pronunciations and same terms, different but similar spellings and pronunciations, choices of spellings or pronunciations seem to largely be influenced by background or personal preferences.

My living in another African country and association with people from different countries has enabled me identify subtle differences in the use of the different types of English ; for example I have observed that uses of words or phrases having the same concept but different terms or expressions; (or) same word, differences in style, connotation and frequency , as shown by examples in the course pack (EUCLID 2021, 30) is mostly influenced by cultural background wherein some people are unable to identify with the usage of certain terms as they lack a cultural identification with those terms. These also apply to grammar construction, euphemistic references, equality vocabulary and politically correct references as shown with examples in page 32 of the course pack (EUCLID 2021, 32). Of particular importance in academic writing, one would have to take note of the differences in punctuation marks and dates to ensure adherence to a particular type and alignment with other aspects of the writing style.

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4) PLAGIARISM

The Merriam Webster Dictionary defines plagiarism as “the act of using another person's words or ideas without giving credit to that person” which agrees with the definition provided in the ACA-401D course pack as “a writer using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 5). This entails use of information and/or ideas covers quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and getting someone to author a paper or an article for you and taking credit for the work done (EUCLID 2021, 5). Though it is almost impossible for students, researchers, etc. to author articles, papers without some form of copying of ideas or information from other sources however the restriction of plagiarism borders on the need to appropriately allocate credit for such works and ideas to the accurate quarters.

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As noted by Copyleaks “despite Plagiarism being a punishable offence since it is a form of intellectual theft, this has not served as a deterrent as it is effortless to plagiarize someone’s work; this holds through whether the word arrangements are changed, or it is presented as a summary or a direct quote as long as the source is not cited, or quotation marks inserted” (Copyleaks, n.d.). This was highlighted to be applicable to previous works by the same author which is referred to as self-plagiarism.

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EUCLID’s stance on having zero tolerance for plagiarism is to be applauded as this will ensure that students like myself develop the relevant skills in making sure that works referenced are properly cited utilizing internationally acceptable styles. The explanations and guidance provided on citations, how to cite and what not to cite were quite explanatory. In addition, I found the information and examples on paraphrasing quite helpful as it could be quite redundant to have too many quotations in a paper with the added effect of taking away from originality of a paper (EUCLID 2021, 6-10). It is equally important to achieve a logical flow as well as achieve a balance between academic and personal styles (EUCLID 2021, 12-13). Having a logical flow and balanced styles ensure that the appropriate ideas are communicated in a manner that enables the reader to follow the ideas to a logical conclusion as desired by the author.

5) THE PLACE OF LATIN EXPRESSIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS IN EVERYDAY USE

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The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill summarizes that “Despite the fact that Latin is no longer the international language of scholars, bits and pieces of it can still be found scattered around” (The Writing Center 2021). Furthermore, going on to point out the need for its continued use in today’s academic world by highlighting “While it’s perfectly acceptable to use English phrases instead of Latin abbreviations, there’s a reason why these abbreviations have survived and continue to be used today: they contain a lot of meaning in a very small package. It takes less time and fewer characters to write e.g., than “for example.” As a bonus, using Latin abbreviations correctly can make your writing

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sound more sophisticated and scholarly” (The Writing Center 2021). In the normal course of professional writing /communication, we inevitably make use of a few of the Latin abbreviations and some of these are more prevalent in certain fields such as legal and medical practice. While I find that the use of Latin as a language is now almost extinct however the surviving parts seem to be mostly the abbreviations with the big three being etc., i.e., and e.g. (The Writing Center 2021). In addition to these, some other commonly used Latin abbreviations and terms include N.B., A.M., P.M., vs, ad hoc, ad lib, de facto, bona fide, and pro bono.

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In exploring the course pack, it was important to me to take on the guidance found in chapter nine of the course pack implying that the use of the Latin terms and abbreviations should be limited to footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing, while the English equivalent of these Latin expressions should be used in business, technical and formal writing (with academic works falling under the formal writing category) (EUCLID 2021, 56).

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While reflecting on this, I had a question about the place of Latin expressions in work related communication such as emails, however I found the clarification on rules applying to the use of these emails by University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill quite helpful, here they observed that “the major style manuals (MLA, APA and Chicago) are in agreement on the need to exclude Latin abbreviations from the main body of a text whether in the ordinary sentences or paragraphs” (The Writing Center). This seems to agree with what I have observed over time that the few Latin terms that make their way into work related communications are usually as an addendum (e.g., the abbreviation N.B.). The exceptions to these I have observed are the big three: etc., i.e., and e.g., which seem to be deemed acceptable by most people as part of the body of regular communication as incorrect as this may be, Curiously the word “addendum,” though has its origin in Latin seems to have made its way into the English language as an acceptable English term.

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6) STYLE GUIDE

It was quite informative to explore the conversation on style guide in chapter seven of the EUCLID course pack. I was able to understand that style guides are essential for formal writing such as technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting while also appreciating that this is primarily informed by a need for consistency across authors utilizing a particular style guideline while minimizing the influence of individual author styles on a finished piece (EUCLID 2021, 24). The argument that some writers believe the ability to follow a consistent writing style should be innate in a writer (EUCLID 2021, 24) is one I can readily identify with as in the course of professional work, I have been able to consistently identify the writer of a piece or a report by his/her unique style even without been made aware of the writer’s identity. However, I defer to the argument that a style guide “helps maintain a consistent style, voice, and tone across your documentation, whether you’re a lone writer or part of a huge docs team” and “can provide guidelines for different documentation deliverables, such as API reference manuals, tutorials, release notes, or overviews of complex technical concepts” (Write the Docs, n.d.).

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Write the Docs further infers that the consistency of tone and style that a style guide provides makes for easier reading and a higher confidence in the author's work. A look at the list of aspects provided for in the scope a style guide such as: preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US for example), use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, structure, etc. would make one appreciate why a style guide could be considered essential for formal publications such as academic papers as these mostly have certain standards for which adherence is required.

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7) CHICAGO STYLE

The Chicago style also known as the Turabian style (when used for research writing) is the style detailed in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press) (EUCLID 2021, 24). Quite noteworthy is the choice of this style by EUCLID which makes it mandatory for students to understand this style as it regulates majority of submissions to be made during my course of study with EUCLID.

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In the EUCLID course pack, Dr. Abel provides a concise guidance for various aspects as regulated under the Chicago style. Interestingly in my academic and professional writing, I have utilized some of these rules without really knowing they were mostly attributed to the Chicago style. The advice to track the use of abbreviations to avoid readers getting confused holds true particularly in instances where these readers may not be familiar with the subject area. Having acronyms properly spelt out when using for the first time also serves to ensure that readers can relate to the acronym whenever it comes along further in the piece. It was also educative to understand the definition and explanation for compounds highlighted as "Compound words are two or more words that work together in a specified order. This order cannot be reversed or rearranged without destroying the compound word's meaning" (EUCLID 2021, 25). However, I observed that close attention had to be paid to the distinctions between full-time and conditional compound words as well as paying attention to presenting words with prefixes appropriately. I also found the guides on italics and quotation marks, quotations, capitalizations, numbers, footnotes, and end notes quite detailed. Mastery of these will improve my writing skills as I progress in my EUCLID course of study.

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8) CONCLUSION

The fundamentals provided in the first study period of ACA-401D have provided me with tools for improving my academic and professional writing skills. The key concepts which engaged me, some of which I have elucidated on above served as eye openers in some cases on how to write in internationally acceptable formats and methods. In other cases, certain concepts, I have previously acquired and interacted with in the course of my professional work and daily living hitherto were validated and more insight provided into their use in a correct and internationally acceptable manner. The aspects of this course

covered in the first study period will facilitate my usage of the correct styles, grammar and writing methods during this program I hope to utilize the skills acquired here in presenting my thesis questions and opinions appropriately, develop the subject matter in an acceptable manner and present my results conclusively while avoiding plagiarism.

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